

RAMAN SCATTERING ENHANCEMENT IN FIBER OPTIC BY CHANGE THE ANGLE OF INCIDENT**¹Ahmed M. Sabri , ²Suha Mousa Khorsheed Al-Awsi**^{1,2} Department of computer technical engineering, Al-Esra'a university college./ Iraq

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Abstract

Due to their ability to avoid issues with free-space beams and optical alignment and because they are generally inexpensive and accessible, optical fibers offer an appealing platform for many application sectors. Raman scattering in fibers make scattering of photons by excited molecules at higher energy levels. Raman scattering's spectrum may be used to identify and analyze materials since it depends on the molecular components present and how they are behaving. Raman scattering has been improved by adjusting all the variables that can affect the amount of scattering and studying the effect of changing the angle of incidence of light on the optical fiber. A specific range of light incidence angles was adopted on the optical fiber, and the spectral outputs of intensity and scattering were observed to derive the best angle. The best angle is the angle at which the Raman scattering is minimal and the light intensity is greatest. When using wavelengths extending from 350-1650nm for light falling on the fiber, it was found that the best angle that gives the best light intensity is 5 degrees, so that the stoke and anti-stoke peaks are appeared in some of them.

Keywords: Optical Fibers, Ramman Scattering, Incident angle, Scattering Enhancement.**1. Introduction**

Optical fibers are cylinder-shaped dielectric waveguides, in which the light can travel along the main axis at optical frequencies. The understanding, design, and production of optical fibers have undergone significant advancements since the first attempts to establish optical guidance in a fiber were made at the turn of the 20th century. This has resulted in a hugely busy field of study as well as numerous applications [1]. Light bending was firstly carried out by the John Tyndall, a British scientist, proved that light could bend across a curved stream of flowing water. in 1854, where, the water let to spew out of a tube. When light reached surface where water and air meetit was entirely mirrored and looked as though it were being carried downhill by the liquid [2]. He had stumbled upon the concept of comprehensive inward introspection, which is the fundamental principle of fiber optics. Figure (1) displays a meridional beam "A" at the crucial angle " θ_c " at the core-cladding contact within the fiber, illustrating Its geometry involved directing a light beam into an optical fiber. It is possible observe the angle at which this beam penetrates the fiber core. " θ_a " towards the fiber axis and undergoes refractive bending prior to the air-core interaction traveling at the crucial angle to the core cladding interface. As a result, any rays that enter As you approach the core-cladding interaction, the fiber core on an angle larger than a will be at a less than " θ_c " angle and won't be

entirely internally reflected. When the incident beam "B" is angled above θ_a is refracted through the cladding and ultimately lost by radiation, which also illustrates this circumstance. Rays therefore need to be incident on the fiber core inside an Cone of acceptance specified by the conical half angle θ_a in order for them to be transmitted by total internal reflection within the fiber core. Therefore, θ_a is also known as the fiber's acceptance angle and is the greatest angle that The fiber may allow light to penetrate in order to propagate [3].

Figure 1 Acceptance angle (θ_a) for light entering an optical cable [3].

The inelastic dispersion of photons occurs during Raman scattering. when they come into contact with materials. As a result, photons that are unreasonably dispersed carry information about the materials' vibrational modes that they come into contact with. This interaction causes photons to either receive energy from molecules that transition from their ground state to their first vibrational stimulated state "(anti-Stokes Raman scattering)" may lose energy in favor of molecules that transition from their ground state to their first vibrational stimulated state "(Stokes Raman scattering)". [4,5]

Raman scattering is brought on by the matrix material's vibrational vibrations interacting with light. First, a photon with $(\hbar\omega_o)$ energy excites the system, causing it to transition from $(E_1=\hbar\omega_o)$ vibronic state to $(E_3=\hbar\omega_S)$ virtual state. Second, Rayleigh scattering happens when a photon with $\hbar\omega_S$ An excited molecule releases energy and de-excited into the $E_2=\hbar(\omega_o-\omega_S)$ final vibronic state where "E2" is similar to "E1." The frequency of the photon then coincides with the frequency of the radiation that was incident. In contrast, inelastic scattering known as Raman scattering will happen when "E2" varies from "E1". Figure(2) shows Stokes $(\hbar\omega_S)$ " and anti-Stokes $(\hbar\omega_{AS})$ "lines, which are produced when spontaneous scattering occurs and occurs when the The dispersed wave's energy differs from the excitation source's "o" for each molecular vibration [6].

Figure 2. Raman scattering is displayed by an energy levels scheme [6].

2. Total Internal Reflections in Optical Fibers

The total internal reflection is a fundamental theory guiding the wave guidance technique in a optical fiber cable. If a beam of light goes from one n_1 -refractive-index media to a n_2 -refractive-index medium, such as air to glass, where n_2 is larger than n_1 the reflected light in the second medium will slant toward the normal. The wave will be deviated from its regular direction toward the surface if n_2 is less than n_1 . If the penetrating beam penetrates the medium either head-on or perpendicular to the surface, it will only totally maintain its initial direction. In this instance when n_2 is less than n_1 , the incident ray will totally reflect inside at some point, indicating that the beam refuses to enter the other material. In the case of the n_2, n_1 instance, the transmitted wave will continue to diverge from the normal if the angle of incidence is continuously increased. However, there is a certain angle, known as the critical angle “ θ_c ”, where there will be a refracted wave positioned at the edge of the two media's boundary and will not enter the second medium. At all angles of larger incidence than the critical angle, the wave is reflected at the boundary. When the incident ray's incident angle is high enough to make the refracted wave really travel back to the original medium, total internal reflection is achieved. By inserting $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$ in Snell's law of refraction, one can determine the crucial angle as follows [12]:

$$n_1 \sin \theta_c = n_2 \sin 90 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\theta_c = \sin^{-1} \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad \dots (2)$$

The meridional rays behave as if they were in a planar waveguide as seen in Figure (3), without altering their angle of incidence, reflect in the same plane as the fiber axis. If the angle “ θ ” between a meridian and the fiber axis is less than the complement of the crucial angle “ $\bar{\theta}_c$ ” given in eq.(3), then a meridian is steered. But, due to “ $n_1 \approx n_2$ ”, the “ $\bar{\theta}_c$ ” is typically tiny with guided beams that are about paraxial [13].

$$\bar{\theta}_c = \pi/2 - \theta_c = \cos^{-1}(n_2/n_1) \quad \dots (3)$$

Figure (3) Meridional ray's path inside the fiber, the beam is directed when $\theta < \theta_c$ [13].

In case when connecting a source to a fiber, it's vital to take these factors into account. Light can be captured by fibers to some extent. The numerical aperture refers to the fiber's capacity to gather light. The intelligence being thusly transferred will be more distorted and its signal, or ray loss, will be bigger with a large numerical aperture (NA) [12]. A decrease in bandwidth also results from an increase in NA. Since the NA depends on the fiber's refractive indices, it is always less than 1. the size of the fiber source and core, the NAs of the fiber and the source, all have an impact on the effectiveness of source-fiber coupling [14].

$$NA = \sqrt{n_1^2 - n_2^2} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$NA = \sin \theta \quad \dots (5)$$

where the refractive index of the core is n_1 and the cladding is n_2 , respectively, θ is the fiber's acceptance cone's half-angle. For step-index fibers, eq.(4) is typically used, whereas for graded index fibers, eq.5 is [14].

3. Related Work

Haiping et al presented an investigation of the angle dependent Raman scattering behavior in chemical vapor transport produced high crystalline NbSe₃ layers. Fitting the temperature coefficient of the Raman peaks by the Gruneisen model provided additional support for the lattice's anharmonicity in the “NbSe₃” crystal. It is shown that the Raman scattering behavior is not significantly affected by changes in ionic locations across the CDW transition [7]. Ying et al investigated the angle-resolved for a 4H silicon carbide (4H-SiC) wafer, the strength of the polarized micro-Raman spectroscopy [8]. Jeremy et al showed that the "fingerprint" left by a molecule's molecular bonds can be used to identify it. Surface enhanced Raman scattering is the perfect

technique for this since it has a limited comprehension of the microscopic world and is essentially unreliable. A new generation of repeatable Raman substrates was optimized in response to the evidence for simultaneous ingoing and outgoing resonances in wavelength and angle. [9]. New two-stage reflective non-imaging dish concentrator "NIDC" proposed by Onubogu et al. is constructed of main and secondary reflecting mirrors that direct light onto optical fibers with high acceptance angles that are near to the concentrator's target. The focused sunlight can be directed through the optical fibers into the building's interior. Design, construction, and evaluation of a new concentrated day lighting system [10]. Worthington conducted an experimental comparison of a fiber acceptance-angle approach and a fiber radiation-angle methodology. Results for the plastic-clad silica fibers and the quasi-step index are provided. The radiation-angle methodology, it is determined, offers ease of use and clear findings, and would thus be a good standard procedure for evaluating optical fibers [11]. The aim of the present work is to find out the best angle of incidence of light on the optical fiber in which the amount of Raman scattering is minimal, while the rest of the scattering types are almost non-existent. This requires first designing and building an optical fiber system, and then experimenting with light falling on it at different angles, calculating the amounts of light scattering, and deducing the optimal situation in which the total dispersion of light is as little as possible.

4. Proposed Fiber Optic Design

The light waves inside optical fiber are simulated to show the total internal reflection in the fiber using Comsol Multiphysics version 5.6 software. The tools available in Comsol give the possibility to design and simulation activity the electromagnetic wave inside waveguide. After opening the program select electromagnetic wave, Beam Envelopes tool is used to compute electric and magnetic field distributions for systems, then the study wavelength domain tool is selected.

Figure (4) shows the established fiber optic model, in which the incoming wave from 300nm - 1600nm wavelength, having a Gaussian profile with a 10 nm beam waist radius, enters the left boundary of a 2D rectangular waveguide of $50\ \mu\text{m}$ width of core, $80\ \mu\text{m}$ width of cladding and $200\ \mu\text{m}$ width of shield and 10 cm length. The wave enters the waveguide at such a small angle of incidence that the propagation angle at the interface between the core ($n=1.9$) of waveguide and the cladding ($n=1.45$) is much larger than the critical angle. Thus, the wave is captured inside the waveguide by TIR. As the waveguide is long compared to the wavelength, the Electromagnetic Waves tool and Beam Envelopes Interface is used to reduce the number of mesh elements required along the propagation direction. The Bidirectional formulation is specifically suited for this model, since there are two wave directions, $\mathbf{k}_1=(k_x, k_y)$ and $\mathbf{k}_2=(k_x, -k_y)$. The wave vector components are $k_x=k_0n\cos(\theta_{in})$, and $k_y=k_0n\sin(\theta_{in})$, where k_0 is the vacuum wave number. and θ_{in} is the incident angle that may change along a range 0 - 90° with step equal to 5° in the core with respect to the boundary normal.

5. Results and Discussion

The proposed optical fiber design described in the previous topic has been adjusted its dimensions and selected the characteristics of its materials in a way that gives us the opportunity to study the possibility of changing the angle of incidence of the light ray only without changing the rest of the factors. Therefore, a specific range was adopted for the values of the angle of incidence of the rays, starting from 0° up to 90°, with a change of 5°. Figures (5) show the results of 24 cases of electric field distribution inside the optical fiber cavity, each time the angle is adjusted by a certain amount for three considered light wavelengths: 250-1650nm . It is clear that there is a regularity in the distribution of the electric field in the cases under study, but what is noticeable is the change in the intensity of the light inside the fiber at each time the incident angle was changed. Figures (6) pictures the front section of the optical fiber for the three considered wavelengths, where the light appeared at the core of the fiber and does not penetrated to the clade. Table (1) represents the intensity of the light inside the cavity of the optical fiber with the change in wavelength with the considered values, while Figures (7) show the distribution of the light intensity inside the fiber with the change of wavelength for each considered angle.

In case of using 0° incident angle, it is noticeable that the progress of the light inside the fiber was uniform and that the highest value of the light intensity was $8.7 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (V}^2/\text{m}^2\text{)}$ at the wavelength 1500nm, which represents the Raman peak, while a second peak was slightly smaller representing the stocks that appeared at the wavelength of 1100nm with an intensity of about $1.26 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (V}^2/\text{m}^2\text{)}$. Whereas, in 5° incident angle the highest intensity of Ramman was $119 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (V}^2/\text{m}^2\text{)}$ appeared at 750nm wavelength, and the intensity of Stokes was $11.2 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (V}^2/\text{m}^2\text{)}$ appeared at 250nm, in which the case of total internal reflection that necessary for penetrating the light through the optical fiber is

noticeable. In case of 15° incident angle, Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 0.025×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $1600nm$, while the two Stokes peaks were appeared with intensities 0.002×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) and 0.0089×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at wavelengths $750nm$ and $1100nm$ frequently. In case of 25° incident angle, Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 0.00203×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $1600nm$, while the two Stokes peaks were appeared with intensities 0.0054×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) and 0.0099×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at wavelengths $550nm$ and $1200nm$ frequently, in which the influence of light from the core to the clade was noticed. In case of 35° incident angle, Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 0.00207×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $350nm$, while the two Anti Stokes peaks were appeared with intensities 0.0074×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) and 0.0014×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at wavelengths $750nm$ and $1100nm$ frequently, in which the appearance of light along the optical fiber was varied, as it did not appear at other wavelengths $550nm$, $850nm$, and $1300nm$. In case of 45° incident angle, Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 0.00206×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $950nm$, while the two Stokes peaks were appeared with intensities 0.0039×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) , 0.00073×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at wavelengths $350nm$ and $650nm$ frequently. Also, there was an Anti Stoke peak appeared with intensity 0.00096×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $1200nm$ wavelength. In such case, the appearance of light along the optical fiber was varied. In case of 60° incident angle, Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 0.00637×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at $1500nm$, and there was a one Stoke peak appeared with intensity 0.00005×10^{-34} (V^2/m^2) at wavelength $550nm$. In such case, it is noticed that the light does not pass through the optical fiber regularly, as it appears tile the clade at certain wavelengths, such as: 450 , 650 , 750 , 850 , 1200 , and $1300nm$, and it does not appear at others, such as: 350 , and $1400nm$. In case of 90° incident angle, the highest Ramman peak was appeared with intensity of 5.4×10^{-102} (V^2/m^2) at $1450nm$, and there was a one Stoke peak appeared with intensity 4.9×10^{-102} (V^2/m^2) at wavelength $550nm$, where the light pass through the optical fiber and vanish at the end of the fiber. As a result, Figure (8) shows the intensity distribution with the change of incident angle, it is shown that the highest intensity is found at 5° incident angle, where there a total internal reflection was happen with Raman distribution at smaller NA (NA =0.087) that leads to small loss and distortion according to eq.(5).

Fig (5)

Fig (6)

Fig (7)

Fig (8)

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